

INTEGRATIVE APPROACH FORM AND METHODS OF DEVELOPING CREATIVE ACTIVITIES OF STUDENTS

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Abstract. *This article describes various forms of methods for developing the creative abilities of students studying in pedagogical universities, based on an integrative approach, that is, pedagogical conditions for future teachers to achieve a high level of education in the future. Based on the analysis, forms and methods for developing students' creative abilities based on an integrative approach, criteria for assessing creative abilities and recommendations for developing students' creative abilities are given.*

Key words: *creativity, integrative approach, pedagogical book, motivation, knowledge and skills.*

Introduction. The main goal of the targeted reforms being implemented in the field of education in our country today is to create broad opportunities for our youth to grow up to be well-rounded. In particular, broad conditions have been created for the formation of the legal framework of the national education system. The fact that ensuring the sustainable quality of education is one of the important directions of state policy can be explained by the following statement of our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev: “We consider it our primary task to improve the activities of all links of the education and upbringing system in accordance with the requirements of today.”

The relevance of an integrative approach to education logically follows from the tasks of education. The main task is to form a holistic picture of the world for students, while the actual educational process is built mainly on a narrow subject, disciplinary basis.

The content of modern higher education should be focused on enriching the methodological aspects of developing students' creative activity. An integrative approach plays an important role in strengthening students' knowledge, skills and qualifications, increasing their interest in the future.

Based on the integrative approach, systematic work is being carried out to train competitive personnel, develop variable forms of training, and implement issues of developing students' creative activity in the process of professional training.

When giving the basics of the integrative approach, it is first necessary to dwell on the concept of integration. According to V.V. Kraevsky, integration is the unification and restoration (from the Latin word *integratio*) of the separate elements of the education system into a single whole, based on the principles of interdependence and complementarity. V.I. Kagan distinguishes the substantive features of the integration process. These include: logical and substantive basis, heterogeneous elements, levels, scale, form.

Main part. In the current education system, the ability of students to achieve high levels of efficiency in their educational and cognitive activities is expanding through the use of integrative approaches.

Currently, the problem of forming an updated educational content through the creation of education based on an integrative approach is becoming increasingly relevant in the education system.

An integrative approach helps to develop students' creative thinking, flexibility in decision-making, and the ability to find new non-standard solutions. In addition, it quickly and effectively prepares students for professional practice, motivates them to use models that teach communication with students. Developing students' creativity through an integrative approach creates an environment that teaches them to concisely and clearly express their work, self-control, and objectively evaluate themselves. In addition, the mutual creative achievements of students develop.

In order to develop students' creative activities based on an integrative approach, it is necessary to create an innovative environment, plan the educational process, motivate and support the achievements and development of students. As a result, in the development of students' creative activity on the basis of an integrative approach, it is ensured that their competitive qualities and knowledge and skills meet the requirements of the time. Under the influence of an integrative approach, the student's personality is formed, life experience and acquired knowledge are combined, social, pedagogical and hereditary factors are interconnected, scientific and pedagogical knowledge and pedagogical influence are integrated, and the unity of upbringing, study and development is ensured.

Education should be carried out through methodological preparation, which has become the main and system-forming link of the whole process. From this it is permissible to highlight the features of student education. These features are manifested in the development of students' creativity and consist in the need to develop students' verbal and non-verbal creativity.

To develop students' creativity, it is necessary to make adjustments to the material being studied, update the content of the lesson, and activate students. Having mastered the technique of competent objective actions in the process of individual or joint analysis of professional tasks, the student develops as a specialist. This is the process of professional training of students, which is a consistent transformation of educational activities aimed at developing creativity into professional activity. The educational process should be structured in such a way that it contains situations that are capable of actualizing the life experience of students and are foreseen.

The process of professional activity determines the future life path of a specialist with a high level of creativity. A specific aspect of the development of creativity during the student period is the formation of specialized creativity during this period. That is, during this period, the motivation to pursue professional activity is combined with the development of cognitive activity in them, the determination and implementation of their own lifestyle, and individualization.

In the study, the technology for developing the creative abilities of students of a higher educational institution was improved by individualizing the educational process aimed at the free manifestation of talent, gradually expanding the possibilities of independent creative research, and giving priority to the consistent identification of the parameters of creativity, analytical and synthetic thinking of professional and motivational activities. The main technologies that we use in the process of developing creativity are: problem-based learning; contextual learning.

The content of developing the creativity of students of a higher educational institution is manifested in the following: developing students' creativity is an important task aimed at increasing their competitiveness and has its own characteristics. Based on the specificity of

developing students' creativity, it is appropriate to highlight the features of education for students of higher education:

firstly, the pedagogical direction of education;

secondly, its component, which is manifested in the development of students' creativity; the content of developing the creativity of students of a higher educational institution is to increase the level of knowledge of students, to have a positive effect on their motivation;

the content of students' professional training is determined on the basis of solving the problem, selecting the necessary teaching technologies, developing the originality and fluency of students' thinking;

To develop students' creativity, we must resort to pedagogical modeling.

Pedagogical modeling is the study of pedagogical objects by modeling the conceptual, procedural, structural and conceptual features and individual aspects of the educational process within a certain socio-cultural space. A model describes the goals of a pedagogical system, process or situation and the main methods of achieving them. In this research work, the technological model of developing creative activities of students of a higher educational institution is improved on the basis of integrating the integrative properties of creative activities and innovative thinking in accordance with educational goals and the vector development of interactive learning, reproductive-risk-taking, creative-research and innovative activities. The problem of choosing pedagogical conditions is of particular importance in the model, which allows us to actually implement the type of activity we need in the technological chain of its design and implementation. The effectiveness of developing creative abilities of students of a higher educational institution is improved on the basis of rational use of existing opportunities for self-development and comparative identification of internal and external psychological characteristics, directions of social relations and stable characteristic qualities of types of activity. The effectiveness of developing creativity in students largely depends on a number of pedagogical conditions. In the course of our scientific research, we put forward the hypothesis that the creative development of preschool students will be effective if the following pedagogical conditions are met: enriching the educational content of preschool students with their own life experience; involving students in professional problem-solving activities; ensuring problem-based learning.

The criteria and indicators of the development of students' creativity are as follows: motivational - a valuable attitude to the future profession; self-expression; motivation to study at the university; cognitive - the amount of students' knowledge in special and pedagogical disciplines, the speed of completing test tasks and the content of the knowledge gained; praxeological - the ability to apply the knowledge gained in practical transformational activities, the ability to deviate from traditional schemes in the process of forming ideas, the ability to create long-range associations, the ability to offer a large number of solutions to a given problem; quickly switch from one task to another.

An integrative approach to the pedagogical process is characterized by influencing a person through a holistic pedagogical method. Such an approach implies knowledge of the content of educational and upbringing processes, as well as appropriate methods, forms and means of activity. Integration, as one of the pedagogical approaches, serves to establish relationships based on the recognition of the dignity of the student's personality, his equality and freedom, and the creation of an atmosphere of collective creative work.

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